

Digital Scholarship Days, four days of learning and collaboration

The Digital Scholarship Centre at the University Library started off 2023 with a bang - 16 workshops over 4 days and more than 200 enthusiastic participants. Digital Scholarship Days contributed to the exchange of knowledge and skills between researchers. Here is a short summary of how the event went.

Digital Scholarship Days was based on workshop contributions from employees at UiO who use digital tools, techniques, and methods in their everyday research, which they wished to share with others. Through a broad call for workshops, sent out in June 2022, we received more than 20 suggested contributions from PhD-fellows, researchers, IT engineers and library staff. The final program consisted of 18 workshops, of which 2 had to be postponed at the last minute due to illness. Both the program and material from the various workshops are held in our collection on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/dsc-uio/>.

The event received 350 registrations from 225 unique participants, both from- and outside of UiO. Some of the workshops had long waiting lists, while others were more narrowly focused and had smaller target groups (e.g., around 10 registered). As expected for events with free participation, there was a dropout of approximately 30%.

The largest group of workshop participants were PhD fellows, 40% (see Fig 1). In total, those holding academic positions at the University (PhD fellows, PostDocs, researchers, and professors) made up 70% of all participants. There was also a large spread in participants' affiliations (see Fig 2), although we plan to work towards broadening and diversifying representation at Digital Scholarship Days in the future.

A large majority of participants reported that they were very satisfied with the workshop they attended and that they expect to be able to apply what they have learned (see Fig 3) as well as that they would recommend others to attend the workshop (Fig 4).

In addition to the actual learning outcomes from the workshop, one of our goals with Digital Scholarship Days was to create a space for networking, relationship-building, and collaboration for people working in various aspects of digital research. The success of this is highlighted in the participant feedback:

“Nice to talk to other participants and instructors during break and lunch. It was good networking.”

As organizers, we observed how the lunch area gathered participants and course instructors around the same table, where conversations could continue after the workshops. The food was also highlighted in the feedback: one participant wrote "Great food!" referring to the selection of both hot and cold vegetarian food, which we tried to make both tasteful and appropriate for all participants.

"Very well organised, happy to have joined!" wrote one participant on the feedback form, to which we would like to say thank you for your participation! We at the DSC would also like

to express our gratitude to everyone who contributed as a workshop host or helper. This event showed us at that we are on the right track when trying to facilitate learning and collaboration across disciplines, and that there is a further need for sharing knowledge on research methods and tools.

Program

Tuesday, January 10th

<u>Time</u> ↓	<u>Session</u>	<u>Location</u>
09:00 - 12:00	<u>Sustainable Authorship in Plain Text using Pandoc and Markdown</u>	<u>GSH: LINKEN</u>
09:00 - 12:00	<u>Informed Consents, Data Classification and Storage</u>	<u>GSH: Elektronisk classroom</u>
09:00 - 12:00	<u>Open Research Data in DataverseNO</u>	<u>GSH: DSC-Oasen</u>
13:00 - 16:00	<u>Creative Data Visualization and Sonification in the Browser</u>	<u>GSH: LINKEN</u>
13:00 - 16:00	<u>Text mining with apps by the Digital Humanities Lab at the National Library of Norway</u>	<u>GSH: Elektronisk classroom</u>
13:00 - 16:00	<u>The Unix shell: tips and tricks to make your life easier</u>	<u>GSH: DSC-Oasen</u>

Wednesday, January 11th

<u>Time</u> ↓	<u>Session</u>	<u>Location</u>
09:00 - 16:00	<u>Databases and SQL</u>	<u>GSH: DSC-Oasen (morning); GSH: LINKEN (afternoon)</u>
09:00 - 12:00	<u>Recording Video/Audio with Yellow and Red Data Needs</u>	<u>GSH: Elektronisk classroom</u>
09:00 - 12:00	<u>Lost in the code? Demystifying R Programming (part 1)</u>	<u>GSH: LINKEN</u>
13:00 - 15:00	<u>InterAct - Discover the undiscovered (discover the unseen)</u>	<u>GSH: DSC-Oasen</u>
15:00 - 17:00	<u>InterAct - Working with text inside interact and inductive coding</u>	<u>GSH: DSC-Oasen</u>

Thursday, January 12th

<u>Time</u> ↓	<u>Session</u>	<u>Location</u>
09:00 - 12:00	<u>Lost in the code?</u> <u>Demystifying R</u> <u>Programming (part 2)</u>	<u>GSH: LINKEN</u>
13:00 - 16:00	<u>Video Visualization</u>	<u>GSH: Elektronisk classroom</u>
13:00 - 16:00	<u>Bibliographic Database</u> <u>Publication and Research</u> <u>Collaboration with Zotero</u>	<u>GSH: LINKEN</u>
13:00 - 16:00	<u>Hands-on introduction to the</u> <u>Python package uniFAIR: a</u> <u>systematic and scalable</u> <u>approach to research data</u> <u>wrangling</u>	<u>GSH: DSC-Oasen</u>

Friday, January 13th

<u>Time</u> ↓	<u>Session</u>	<u>Location</u>
09:00 - 16:00	<u>Quarto - Next Generation R</u> <u>Markdown</u>	<u>GSH: LINKEN</u>
09:00 - 12:00	<u>Programming in Practice:</u> <u>Bad luck, Drug or Heart -</u> <u>Computational models to the</u> <u>rescue</u>	<u>GSH: Elektronisk classroom</u>
09:00 - 12:00	<u>Create and Handle Data</u> <u>Management Plans with the</u> <u>Data Stewardship Wizard</u>	<u>GSH: DSC-Oasen</u>
14:00 - 15:30	<u>How to make better graphs</u> <u>and figures</u>	<u>GSH: DSC-Oasen</u>